

HEALTHCARE WASTE AND EXPIRED MEDICINES: A REVIEW OF RISKS, PRACTICES, AND REGULATORY APPROACHES

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Abstract

Proper drug disposal is a critical component of both public health and environmental protection. Improper disposal of medications contributes to environmental contamination, accidental poisonings, and drug misuse, with severe consequences for humans, animals, and ecosystems. This study aimed to evaluate safe disposal practices for pharmaceutical waste and explore possible outreach and policy strategies to minimize risks associated with current disposal methods.

Safe disposal of tablets and capsules typically involves removing them from original packaging, mixing them with undesirable substances (e.g., coffee grounds or cat litter), sealing them in a container or bag, and discarding them in household trash. Bottles, vials, and other containers should undergo steam autoclaving or incineration, while empty containers require triple rinsing, labeling as “empty” or “defaced,” and subsequent disposal. Syringe disposal is a major health concern, as unsafe practices can cause needle-stick injuries and facilitate transmission of infections; patient education programs and provision of sharps disposal containers are therefore essential. Bandages and dressings, composed of multilayer polymers and cellulose, are challenging to recycle but can be managed by hydro pulping. Cytotoxic and chemotherapy waste is disposed of through thermo-sterilization, incineration, or return to pharmacy programs.

The U.S. Food and Drug Administration (FDA) recommends several disposal options, including medicine take-back programs, household trash disposal, and flushing of high-risk medicines such as narcotic patches to prevent accidental exposure. However, flushing pharmaceuticals contributes to aquatic toxicity, beta-lactam resistance, and reduced fertility in fish, raising serious ecological concerns. Although burning is occasionally practiced, it is not recommended due to environmental hazards.

Overall, appropriate pharmaceutical disposal is essential to reduce environmental pollution, prevent antimicrobial resistance, and safeguard public health. Strengthening awareness, infrastructure, and regulatory compliance offers a feasible pathway to safer management of pharmaceutical waste.

INTRODUCTION

Proper drug disposal is a critical aspect of healthcare waste management, with direct implications for public

health and environmental protection. Inappropriate practices, such as flushing medications into toilets,

discarding them in household waste, or leaving them unsecured, pose significant risks including environmental contamination, drug diversion,

accidental ingestion, and the spread of antimicrobial resistance [1-4].

Figure 1 : Wrong disposal of medicines

Environmental and Public Health Concerns

Pharmaceuticals discarded into wastewater systems have been detected in rivers, lakes, and groundwater due to the inability of conventional treatment plants to remove these compounds effectively [2,6]. Persistent drug residues, including antibiotics and hormones, disrupt aquatic ecosystems, reduce fertility in fish, and contribute to the emergence of antibiotic-resistant bacteria. Flushing estrogen-containing medications, for example, has been linked to decreased reproductive capacity in aquatic species, threatening biodiversity. Moreover, burning pharmaceutical waste at low temperatures releases toxic pollutants, while poorly designed landfill sites may lead to leaching of harmful chemicals into soil and water.

From a public health perspective, unsafe storage and disposal of unused medicines, particularly opioids, contribute to their diversion and misuse. Studies show that many individuals obtain prescription opioids for non-medical use from family or friends,

often from home medicine cabinets [3,5]. This misuse has fueled the opioid crisis globally. Similarly, unsafe syringe disposal in household trash or public spaces exposes children and healthcare workers to needle-stick injuries and bloodborne infections .

Current Disposal Practices

Several strategies exist for managing pharmaceutical waste, although implementation varies across countries. Solid dosage forms such as tablets and capsules are recommended to be removed from packaging, mixed with undesirable substances (e.g., cat litter, coffee grounds), sealed in containers, and discarded with household trash, unless take-back programs are available [6-8]. Containers, bottles, and vaccine vials may be managed through steam autoclaving, incineration, landfilling, or encapsulation with cement mixtures [9-13]. Safe syringe disposal requires leak-proof, puncture-resistant sharps containers and patient education programs to minimize unsafe practices [14-16].

How to Dispose Needles & Syringes

<p>Seal it properly</p>	
<p>Empty or dispose at a designed collection site</p>	

Figure 2: Safe disposal of medicines

Bandages and dressings, often made of complex polymers, can be managed through hydro pulping for recycling [17]. Cytotoxic and chemotherapy waste is disposed of via thermo-sterilization, high-temperature

incineration, packed in chemotherapeutic bags or return-to-pharmacy programs [18].

Figure 3: Chemotherapeutic Bags for waste disposals

Regulatory and Policy Measures

The U.S. Food and Drug Administration (FDA) recommends three primary approaches: medicine take-back programs, household trash disposal, and flushing of certain high-risk medicines such as fentanyl patches to prevent accidental exposure [21,22]. However, flushing has raised ecological concerns, particularly regarding antimicrobial resistance and aquatic toxicity [23,24]. Take-back programs and pharmacy drop-boxes have proven effective in reducing drug diversion and minimizing environmental contamination, though challenges remain in awareness, infrastructure, and regulatory enforcement, especially in low- and middle-income countries [25,26].

Study Rationale

Despite the availability of safe disposal guidelines, gaps in implementation persist globally. In countries such as Pakistan, improper disposal practices, reliance on incineration and landfilling, and lack of standardized protocols exacerbate environmental and public health risks. Therefore, this study explores existing disposal methods, their advantages and limitations, and potential outreach and policy options to promote safe pharmaceutical waste management and reduce associated harms.

Methodology:

This study employed a narrative review approach to evaluate pharmaceutical waste disposal practices and their associated public health and environmental implications. Relevant data were collected from peer-reviewed journal articles, reports, and official guidelines issued by international agencies such as the World Health Organization (WHO), the United States Food and Drug Administration (FDA), and Health Care Waste Management (HCWM) frameworks. Literature published between 2000 and 2024 was considered, with inclusion criteria focusing on studies that addressed pharmaceutical waste management, environmental contamination, and public health risks, while older or non-English publications without direct relevance were excluded. The retrieved information was categorized into thematic areas, including environmental and public health risks, disposal of different dosage forms, handling of syringes and cytotoxic drugs, and international disposal guidelines. Comparative analysis was also carried out to highlight differences between developed and developing countries, with a particular focus on Pakistan as a case study.

Results:

The findings of this review indicate that improper pharmaceutical disposal contributes significantly to environmental and public health risks. Flushing medications and discarding them in household trash were found to contaminate water systems with antibiotics, hormones, and analgesics, with evidence of reduced fertility in fish populations and the persistence of pharmaceutical residues due to inadequate wastewater treatment.

From a public health perspective, unsecured storage and disposal of opioids in households contributed to widespread misuse, as many individuals accessed unused prescriptions from family and friends. Similarly, unsafe disposal of syringes in domestic waste and public spaces was linked to needle-stick injuries and the transmission of infections (25-28).

In Pakistan and other developing countries, hospitals primarily relied on incineration and landfilling, although poorly constructed landfills often caused leaching of toxic compounds into soil and groundwater. In contrast, developed nations had greater reliance on structured interventions such as drug take-back programs, pharmacy drop-boxes, and encapsulation techniques for cytotoxic drugs and vaccine vials, which reduced both environmental contamination and diversion of medicines for misuse (29-30).

Despite these strategies, gaps remained across healthcare systems, including limited public awareness, insufficient training of healthcare providers in disposal protocols, and inconsistent implementation of international guidelines, particularly in low-resource settings.

Discussion:

These results highlight that the consequences of improper pharmaceutical disposal extend beyond environmental contamination to critical public health concerns. The persistence of active pharmaceutical ingredients in aquatic systems, coupled with the rise of antimicrobial resistance, underscores the urgent need for safer disposal methods. The evidence linking household storage of opioids to community misuse further reflects the importance of structured disposal systems that prevent diversion. Developed countries that have invested in take-back initiatives, pharmacy-based drop-boxes, and advanced waste treatment have

demonstrated reductions in both misuse and environmental contamination (31-32).

Conversely, low- and middle-income countries remain heavily reliant on outdated or unsafe practices such as open dumping and poorly managed incineration, which exacerbate risks of groundwater pollution and community exposure. The findings also suggest that public awareness and healthcare worker training are equally vital to infrastructure, as disposal guidelines alone are insufficient without active compliance. Moreover, specialized pharmaceutical waste, particularly cytotoxic drugs and sharp materials, requires stricter oversight and tailored interventions to prevent occupational hazards and long-term toxicity (33-35). The role of pharmacists is central to bridging these gaps, as they can provide disposal education, act as collection points for unused medicines, and help integrate safe disposal practices into routine patient care.

Conclusion:

Improper pharmaceutical disposal represents a dual threat to environmental safety and public health. Evidence shows that unsafe disposal contributes to antimicrobial resistance, water contamination, accidental poisonings, and the diversion of controlled substances. While developed countries have implemented structured programs such as take-back initiatives and pharmacy drop-boxes, developing nations continue to face challenges with incineration, landfilling, and lack of awareness. To address these issues, a multi-pronged approach is necessary—one that combines infrastructure, regulatory enforcement, public education, and professional training. Pharmacists and healthcare providers are central to this strategy, ensuring that proper disposal practices are not only available but actively implemented. Strengthening these systems globally can minimize the risks associated with pharmaceutical waste and safeguard both ecosystems and human health.

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